

The role of higher education attributes in students' brain drain intentions.

The case of a Western Balkan country

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1. Introduction

During the last two decades, Balkan countries have been facing an increasing emigration of youngsters looking to continue their professional careers abroad, especially in the European Union, producing the incident of brain drain (Regional Cooperation Council, 2020). The Republic of Macedonia particularly recognises a massive flow of younger generations who decide to leave the country for potentially enhanced studying or working opportunities. One of the main reasons for this choice is the inadequate educational resources failing to provide the most effective learning environments for students (Council of Europe Development Bank, 2021). Nevertheless, the current brain drain literature has been restricted to merely describing migration prototypes and destination preferences, exploring the socio-demographic and economic motives for moving abroad, and failing to explain the actual reasons behind brain drain intentions (Fumasoli, 2021; Gesing & Glass, 2019; Ilic & Milosavljevic, 2018). Hence, given that most of the brain drain in Western Balkan consists of students or recent graduates, it becomes necessary to address the obstacles that discourage young people from living and prospering in their country, primarily focusing on higher education as the environment where brain drain tendency arises (WFD, 2019).

This study's research question aims to identify students' perceptions of the higher education institutions and professors, as determined by their previous expectations and social influence, simultaneously shaping their intentions to leave the country for a better professional future. The

relevant background in education quality literature claims that future intentions are fundamentally forged by personal beliefs, expectations or the social surrounding (MacRae & Sawatzky, 2020). Thus, building on the Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) (Bandura, 1977), the development of the proposed model assumes that environmental and personal factors interrelate in the formation of students' behavioural responses related to their professional progress (Bennett et al., 2020). The implications driven by this research contribute to an innovative observation of higher education services to reduce the brain drain tendency in Western Balkans.

The remainder of the study describes the theoretical foundation for the proposed research (section 2), followed by the methodology (section 3) and the results (section 4), to close with the discussion of the conclusions and the implications of the investigation (section 5).

2. Theoretical background

2.1. The brain drain problem in Western Balkans

The current economic and social development in the Western Balkans has led to an increased intention of students and recent graduates to move abroad to seek employment opportunities. This tendency, known as brain drain, has been affecting Western Balkan countries for two decades, presenting a frequent emigration of the young population from the Western Balkans to the European Union or the United States (Ilic & Milosavljevic, 2018). It describes the inclination of individuals to leave their country, usually in search of better professional opportunities (Council of Europe Development Bank, 2021). To this point of the brain drain literature, these intentions have been contemplated as consequences of socio-demographic and economic reasons that push students towards turnover, or enclosed the description of migration patterns and choices of destination to continue the professional career (Fitzpatrick & Jones, 2016; McGill, 2018). Moreover, it has been recognised that most of the brain drain in Western Balkan consists of students or fresh graduates, stating the higher education institutions as the leading ones responsible for diverting highly qualified professionals to foreign countries (Naumovski, 2021; Šlaus et al., 2004). What is more, the brain drain intentions have been increasingly related to poor institutional quality and critical social infrastructure, among which education is considered an eroding element, raising in this way the need to explore if the problem emerges in the higher education system (WFD, 2019).

2.2. Social cognitive theory for tackling brain drain

Generally, behavioural intentions have mainly been influenced by individual observations and perceptions, which have been greatly induced by the setting they act in (MacRae & Sawatzky, 2020). Like this, the environment can be described by different elements, such as those coming from personal beliefs or experiences, social surroundings, or higher education expectations. In this sense, students' perceptions of higher education quality, efficacy or reputation, have been mentioned as relevant factors to consider leaving the country for better professional opportunities. However, the research on those relationships is still extremely scarce (Council of Europe Development Bank, 2021). Furthermore, individuals' impressions of themselves or the opinion of their closest social circle, have shown to be relevant influencers in the decision-making related to brain drain actions (Ashrafi et al., 2020).

Therefore, to identify the repercussions to youngsters' intentions to leave their country, the SCT was considered in understanding and predicting their behavioural changes (Bandura, 1977), describing conduct through a triadic interaction among the individuals' behaviour, their personal attributes and the environmental influences (Du, Zhu and Zheng, 2021). According to the SCT, the environmental factors work as events that incite particular comportment, supported simultaneously by personal characteristics or circumstances (Almuqrin & Mutambik, 2021). Therefore, the behavioural responses are believed to be 'the result of (a) self-perception that interacts with the environment (Bandura, 1986) and (b) self-knowledge and social knowledge that generate the motivational basis of actions (Blackburn & Lawrence, 1995)' (Gaikwad, 2021, 182). Hence, individuals' behaviour becomes a dynamic system of interrelations with their subjective cognition and the social environment where they act. Indeed, this behaviour becomes projected by individuals' perceptions and expectations regarding the setting (Ma et al., 2020).

The previous actions, promoting continuous learning and development, have been associated with the perceptions and knowledge of the higher education service consumption and students' interaction with professors, where the SCT provides a comprehensive way to identify and adjust individual behaviours (Bippus et al., 2003; Ma et al., 2020; Watt & Richardson, 2020). Thus, this approach proves appropriate for reinforcing the understanding of students' personal or social anticipations and their perceptions of the studies' elements, allowing us to explain their professional development and job prospects (Alzahrani & Seth, 2021). In line with this, we argue

that students' expectations about the educational service and their perceptions of the subjective norms risen from their social relationships - as the *personal factors* revealing individual prospects, will influence their view of the quality of higher education institutions and the professors' accessibility - as the *environmental factors* describing the higher education system. These personal and environmental elements will explain students' tendency for leaving the country – as the *behavioural outcome* of the mentioned influences.

Consequently, bearing in mind the lack of research on the impacts on youngsters' intentions to move abroad, this study contributes to closing the research gap in mitigating the brain drain in the Western Balkans, by identifying the relevance of students' social interactions, their expectations and the evaluation of the higher education system (Bennett et al., 2020).

2.3. Hypotheses development

The investigation of individual personal aspects provides evidence for their vital role in tracing behavioural intentions (Prakash, 2018). Some of the personal elements found as the protagonist in students' higher education perception and related constancy are their previous expectations regarding the benefits of the system and their surrounding opinions (Kaboudi et al., 2017). These personal and societal factors of the students as the consumers of the system are interrelated to the perceived educational quality of the institution and the professors, as well as their prospects for future professional decisions (Tan et al., 2016).

Accordingly, higher education institutions have addressed students' expectations by searching for educational quality and resources (Prakash, 2018). They are deemed as indicators for universities to determine quality elements they should focus on, and describe students' perception of the importance of education features, such as the possibility of finding a job which is expected to be well-paid, need for knowledge or involvement in research and development (Río-Rama et al., 2021). Previous research on higher education has corroborated that individuals' expectations directly influence the perceived quality of the service (Shahsavari & Sudzina, 2017).

Moreover, students' perceptions and expectations regarding the education system elements have been proven to be critical determinants of student-professor interaction assessment (Bippus et al., 2003). If this communication is initially perceived by students as rewarding, it is expected for professors' availability to be considered in the educational system assessment, which in turn will generate behavioural responses related to their future professional formation (Pfund et al., 2013).

In this sense, professors' skills and assistance in providing the higher education service should align with students' expectations, so future career opportunities would be perceived as favourable (Paposa & Paposa, 2022).

Hence, students' expectations will simultaneously influence their perceptions of the educational system quality and loyalty behaviours, meaning that if students' expectations are met, they will likewise present behavioural responses with the aim of continuation, rather than leaving the country (Río-Rama et al., 2021).

Attending the SCT, we recall the influence of students' personal factors as determinants of quality perceptions in the higher education environment, and their joint impact on behavioural responses, to advocate the following hypothesis:

H1: Students' expectations regarding education will impact their perception of (a) the educational quality, (b) professors' availability for interaction, and (c) their intentions to leave the country.

The subjective norms describe an individual perception of their close social network's beliefs about whether the individual should engage in a concrete behaviour (Narteh et al., 2017). It has been broadly confirmed the relevance of significant others' opinions about the higher education environment, and it is believed to be a significant influencer of students' perceptions of and activities in that environment (Cicha et al., 2021).

Subjective norms are considered to influence students' prospects and observations of the system, further giving rise to professional future decision-making (Ashrafi et al., 2020). Accordingly, students perceive their surrounding's opinions as important and strive to fulfil their expectations (Marinkovic & Kalinic, 2017). Therefore, family or close friends' opinions regarding the professional opportunities offered by the higher education system can highly determine how students perceive the higher education quality and professors' resources, likewise influencing their choices to leave the country (Rejón-Guardia et al., 2020).

Namely, social networks' expectations about the educational and professors' capacities, and the encouragement for students to migrate out of their home country for work, are proven to influence students' perceptions of the educational service they receive from the universities and their migratory and career decisions (Nguyen, 2020). The impression of parents, family or other influential persons for the student regarding professional migration, will have an indicative

influence on students' views of the educational relevance and aptitude of the institution, appointing as well their turnover choices (Buchenrieder et al., 2020).

With this in mind, following the SCT groundwork, personal factors will impact individuals' perceptions about the higher education environment and their behavioural outcomes, supporting the proposition of the following hypothesis:

H2: Subjective norms about brain drain will impact students' perception of (a) the educational quality, (b) professors' availability for interaction, and (c) students' intentions to leave the country.

The institution's quality, prosperity and differentiation from other universities significantly influence different individual observations and outcomes (Belando-Montoro et al., 2022; Volkwein & Parmley, 2000). Additionally, professors' resources, designating the core educational quality, capture the perceptions of the higher education service delivery (Teeroovengadum et al., 2016). Accordingly, higher education assessment is mainly associated with students' experience with the university environment quality, such as the course, faculty and university service and accreditation (Mandernach, 2015). Students perceive the higher education institution quality as key in evaluating the educational process and decision-making (Prakash, 2018). They recognise it as the necessary educational element for determining committed continuance behaviour (Duque, 2014).

The professors' interaction with students, in turn, refers to professors' accessibility and availability outside of formal instruction. It describes the degree to which students perceive their professors as socially approachable and keen on interaction with them, external of obligatory communication. This aspect is seen as fundamental for students' higher education assessment (Bippus et al., 2003). Therefore, the level of the education service quality and the interaction with professors, will form the key elements affecting students' perceptions and responses (Manatos et al., 2017). They have been identified as predictors of students' loyalty, confidence in career choices, persistence and professional dedication, and even regulators of attrition rates or dropout intentions (Gupta et al., 2020). If those are deemed poor and insufficient, it is expected to result in adverse behavioural outcomes obstructing students' continuance choices, emphasising their need for enriching educational practices for professional development abroad (Crisp & Cruz, 2009; Duque, 2014; Prakash, 2018).

To highlight the triadic effect proposed in the SCT, the impact of the environmental factors on behavioural outcomes is likewise described, meaning that individuals' observation of the higher education environment is expected to influence their intentions, offering background for the subsequent hypotheses:

H3: The perceived education quality will impact students' intentions to leave the country.

H4. The perceived professors' availability for interaction will impact students' intentions to leave the country.

The assumptions mentioned above are shown in the diagram below (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Proposed research model

3. Methodology

3.1. Procedure

To create the survey, a review of the literature was conducted to uncover and identify higher education aspects shaping students' perceptions of the system's outcomes. Furthermore, to pre-test the relevance and precision of the constructed questionnaire, 10 researchers and professors from the field of higher education and 10 university students were consulted. To minimise misunderstandings and assure the clarity of the statements, the final questionnaire was double-checked by the participants in the pre-test. The target population for this study were students from public universities in the Republic of Macedonia. All students provided their views on the higher

education services available at the degree level they were presently pursuing and their impressions of the institution.

All measurements were taken using 5-point Likert scales (ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). The scales were adapted to the context of higher education and are validated in the previous literature. They have their base in the following studies: Banciu, Banciu and Potolea (2015), Bauer et al. (2005), Volkwein and Parmley (2000), Bippus et al. (2003), and Barrett and Yates (2002) and (Kizito et al., 2015), for students' expectations, subjective norms, the perceived higher education quality, professors' availability, intention to leave the country, respectively.

For the data analysis, partial least square structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) was employed, meeting the specified implementation criteria (Sarstedt et al., 2017). The evaluation was done with a high-level SEM tool for R (4.0.5), while the descriptive analysis was done with Python 3.7.

3.2. Sample

A total of 1150 students participated in the investigation. The respondents were chosen using a purposive non-probabilistic sampling approach, as it was the most appropriate method for obtaining the predetermined group with precise characteristics, such as higher education students (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2010). A sampling error of $\pm 2.89\%$, at a 95% confidence level for the case of maximum uncertainty, was calculated. Power analysis using the G*Power program was used to confirm the suitability of the sample size. The obtained power was 99.99%, for a standard significance level of 0.05, effect size $f^2 = 0.15$, and four predictors, well above the suggested power threshold of 80% (Cohen, 1988; Faul et al., 2007).

Table 1 shows the socio-demographic and economic characteristics of the participants. The respondents' background information reveals that 64% of the participants were women, and 36% were men. Most of them lived in Skopje (47.8%) and attended the Ss. Cyril and Methodius University (65.5%). The majority of responders (65.5%) were solely focused on their studies and financially reliant on their parents (72.5%).

[Table 1 near here]

4. Results

4.1. Measurement model assessment

To measure the dependability of individual items, standardised loadings (λ) were confirmed to fulfil a threshold of 0.6 as the minimum value for the item to be considered relevant, all significant at a level of 95% (Hair et al., 2016). RhoA ($\rho_A > 0.7$) (Dijkstra & Henseler, 2015) and Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha > 0.7$) (Hair et al., 2019) were estimated to validate construct dependability. Convergent validity was corroborated by calculating the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) ($AVE > 0.5$) (Fornell & Larcker, 1981) of each construct. Table 2 illustrates all the measurement items' values and the validation of the scales' reliability and internal consistency.

[Table 2 near here]

Adhering to recommendations by Henseler, Ringle and Sarstedt (2015), discriminant validity was determined by evaluating the correlations using the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT). All HTMT correlations, presented in Table 3, show values lower than 0.90, supporting the model's discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2015; Kline, 2011).

[Table 3 near here]

4.2. Structural model assessment

After evaluating the measurement model, the coefficient of determination was used to examine the prediction accuracy (R^2). According to Cohen (1992), R^2 values higher than 0.26 are regarded as significant, obtaining for this model $R^2=0.27$ for institution quality, $R^2=0.02$ for professors' availability, and $R^2=0.34$ for intention to leave the country.

T-values and standard errors were calculated using a bootstrapping technique of 5,000 interactions to assess statistical validity. According to the findings presented in Table 4, seven of the eight path coefficients are significant. Students' expectations impact higher education quality perceptions (H1a: 0.124, $p < 0.001$) and intention to leave the country (H1c: $\beta = -0.083$, $p < 0.01$). Subjective

norms exhibit significant effect on higher education quality perceptions (H2a: $\beta=-0.124$, $p<0.001$), professors' availability (H2b: $\beta= 0.128$, $p<0.001$) and intention to leave the country (H2c: $\beta= 0.512$, $p<0.001$). Students' intention to leave the country, in turn, is influenced by higher education quality (H3: $\beta=-0.216$, $p<0.001$) and professors' availability (H4: $\beta= -0.064$, $p<0.05$). The one hypothesis that was not confirmed is the path from students' expectations to professors' availability (H1b). As it can be observed, the paths from subjective norms and higher education quality to intention to leave the country, show the greatest impact. This implies that students' intention to leave the country is influenced by the opinions of their family and friends, and their own perceptions regarding the quality of the higher education they attend.

[Table 4 near here]

Schwarz's BIC (Schwarz, 1978) is a well-known general approach for defining and choosing the final model, as the rule to follow is that the model improves as the BIC value decreases. The BIC for intention to leave the country in the final research model provided in this study is -446, for institution quality -337, and for professors' availability the value is 1.08. These measures imply that professors' availability is not as well-modelled as the other constructs, which is to be anticipated given that it is the only path that is not supported.

Finally, observing the mediating position of the higher education quality and professors' availability in the model, a post-hoc mediation analysis was performed to investigate the indirect impact of student expectations and subjective norms on intention to leave the country. The indirect impact values in Table 5 reveal that three out of the four indirect paths are significant. The one not significant mediating effect, proposing the influence of students' expectations on intention to leave the country through professors' availability, is understood given the implication of the not supported H1b.

[Table 5 near here]

To summarise, students' intention to leave the country is influenced directly by their educational expectations, perceived professors' availability, subjective norms, and higher education quality

perception. Subjective norms and students' expectations also impact perceived higher education quality, just as subjective norms have an impact on professors' availability.

Finally, extensive analysis was carried out in order to look for potential connections between a specific set of control variables. Gender, residence, students' employment situation and financial support for the studies were all considered control variables, based on previous research claiming their potential impact (Hornstein Tomi et al., 2018; Yavuz et al., 2017). Each of the control variables was estimated by adding the variable's link to the dependent variable of intention to leave the country, to evaluate if it would change the model's validity in any way. The control analyses reveal the following results for: gender ($\beta = -0.009$, $p = 0.697$), residence ($\beta = -0.012$, $p = 0.635$), employment situation of the students ($\beta = 0.010$, $p = 0.692$), financial support for the studies ($\beta = 0.003$, $p = 0.911$). The proposed relationships were not affected by any of the control variables.

5. Discussion

As the existing migrant population grows, youngsters use the given possibilities to study or work abroad, leading to a phenomenon known as brain drain, where highly educated and competent individuals leave their country (Western Balkans Democracy Initiative, 2021). This issue has impacted Western Balkans for over two decades, requiring serious research on the factors inducing this trend (Fumasoli, 2021; Ilic & Milosavljevic, 2018). Building on the SCT, which postulates a triadic relationship among environmental, personal and behavioural factors, this research explores students' inclination to study abroad (behavioural outcome), from the viewpoint of the higher education system quality in terms of service and human resources (environment), besides the personal or social expectations (personal factors).

The findings of the survey carried out with 1150 university students in the Republic of Macedonia support seven of the eight proposed hypotheses. Namely, it was confirmed that the intention to leave the country is directly influenced by students' expectations (H1c), subjective norms (H2c), higher education quality perception (H3) and professors' availability (H4). These findings are consistent with previous research, indicating that these constructs could play an essential role in students' evaluation of the higher education system and professional responses (Kaboudi et al., 2017; Río-Rama et al., 2021). Regarding students' expectations, when these are fulfilled, such as their knowledge demands being met and career opportunities being accessible, they are more inclined to stay in their country. Furthermore, subjective norms significantly influence students'

intention to leave the country. As confirmed by Merchant, Kumar and Mallik (2017), important reference groups pass on their values and views about the profession and life goals to their close ones, which influence the latter's decisions, such as the decision to emigrate abroad. As expected, this study finds a significant association between perceived higher education quality and the intention to leave the country. Higher education quality is the only direct path to intention to leave the country with a negative path coefficient, implying that as the perceptions regarding the institution's quality improve, fewer students will want to leave the county. Moreover, the relationship between professors' availability and students' intention to leave the country has been proven, suggesting that professors' efforts to be more dedicated to the students have a significant impact on students' perspectives (Duque, 2014). Nevertheless, if the expectation about the interaction with professors is not previously considered an important asset and a worthwhile experience, the assessment of professors' availability might not even take place, therefore not influencing turnover intentions (Bippus et al., 2003).

In addition, students' expectations positively impact their perception of higher education quality (H1a). According to previous research, top-down processes like expectations have a relevant impact on perception and decision-making (Williams, 2007), indicating that students' expectations could be crucial for shaping the actual perceptions (Yousapronpaiboon, 2014). The path from subjective norms to institution quality has a negative effect (H2a), showing that the opinions of others have a detrimental influence on how students perceive higher education quality. People from Western Balkan countries may be proclive to underestimate Macedonian higher education and to emphasise the value of foreign education institutions to see leaving the country as a better professional chance (King & Oruc, 2019). The same factor could explain the association between subjective norms and professors' availability (H2b). It shows that the subjective norms that promote emigration reflects into students' perceptions about the quality of their university and professors' capacities.

5.1. Academic and managerial implications

The present study has addressed significant academic and managerial implications. First, the study contributes to the monitoring of the brain drain process. Currently, most brain drain research is restricted to the social and economic determinants, which is why we approached the subject from a different perspective, that of education, as the potential reason for youngsters' tendency to leave

the country (Ilic & Milosavljevic, 2018). Second, the educational viewpoint refers to how students view their university, the professors and quality, describing the system as a whole, as well as how this might affect their brain drain intentions. In this way, through the lens of higher education, the study contributes to a better understanding of the Macedonian educational system's potential. Third, the study looked at the reference groups' opinions as the background influence on the brain drain proclivity of students in the Republic of Macedonia. According to our findings, students consider their friends and family's views about the possible choice to migrate. This reveals that subjective norms can impair students' decisions, making them more likely to leave the country, as related research has suggested (Omic & Handeland, 2021). Finally, with its vast sample size, this research adds to the literature on higher education in the Western Balkans, offering knowledge for improving educational conditions and assisting brain-drain prevention initiatives and policies.

Additionally, the practical implications of the study's findings are important to be considered from a managerial perspective. Students who feel academically well-prepared will prove more confident about their achievements and future performance (Duque, 2014). Hence, students who have high expectations for the university to which they are applying perceive the quality of their institution to be higher than those who have low expectations. Students who believe that the university will help them find a job quickly, especially one that pays well, and that will satisfy their need for knowledge, have a more favourable perception of the university's quality. That means universities should tailor their services to students' expectations and try to carry out public interventions, such as raising their community profile, sharing impact stories, and even embracing openness, so that students have more genuine expectations, resulting in a better perception of the institution's quality.

Furthermore, according to the findings of this study, subjective norms imposed by family and friends impact students' intentions and views, particularly if they believe students who leave the country are making wise and valuable decisions. This implies that higher education institutions and the country should try to promote the value of Macedonian higher education and highlight the benefits of staying in the country. The greater the recognition and educational excellence of the institution, on the one side, and the professors' resources and capacities for adequate interaction with students, on the other, the higher the probability for students to perceive a more valuable higher education system worthy of being part of. Additionally, by raising awareness about the long-term benefits of staying in the county, listing an enhanced region's economic

competitiveness, labour productivity, capacity to innovate and technologically progress, students and their close ones could be convinced of the advantage of studying and working in the Republic of Macedonia, contributing in this way to its growth and development (Ristovska et al., 2018).

5.2. Limitations and future research

A few limitations of this study might be addressed in future research. To begin with, this study focuses on students' perceptions of the educational system and higher education institutions, and how they influence their aspirations about brain drain. This study might be enhanced by widening the survey to students who have already left the country, giving a more complete picture. Another limitation is that all the students are from the Republic of Macedonia, making the results difficult to generalise. Nevertheless, this opens an opportunity to explore the brain drain for the whole of Western Balkan and compare and better understand the trend occurring in the region.

Furthermore, considering variables such as institutional support and organisational structure will offer a possibility to examine the education system from an additional perspective evaluating the role of the institution's format (e.g., public vs private universities) in the brain drain intention. Finally, this research focuses solely on students' opinions of the higher education system, making the evaluation one-sided. For future research, opinions and perceptions from the professors' perspectives could be analysed, so that both standpoints can be compared in order to get a more objective representation of higher education in the Republic of Macedonia.

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Table 1. Socio-demographic profile of respondents

Characteristic		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	414	36
	Female	736	64
Residence	Skopje	550	47.8
	Shtip	60	5.2
	Strumica	59	5.1
	Bitola	52	4.5
	Kumanovo	57	5
	Other	372	32.4
University	University Ss. Cyril and Methodius	753	65.5
	University Goce Delchev	316	27.5
	Other	81	7
Faculty	Electrical Engineering	121	10.5
	Medicine	287	25
	Law	119	10.4
	Informatics	220	19.1
	Other	403	35
Year	First	230	20
	Second	268	23.3
	Third	295	25.7
	Fourth	227	19.7
	>Fourth	130	11.3
Working and studying	Yes	397	34.5
	No	753	65.5
Who finances the studies	Themselves	245	21.3
	Parents	834	72.5
	Scholarship	71	6.2

Construct name and measurement items	λ (loadings)
<i>Students' expectations when choosing the degree</i> (AVE=.55; α=.79; rhoA=.79)	
Easiness in finding a job.	0.650
Well-paid job.	0.684
Need for knowledge.	0.809
Involvement in research and development.	0.773
Spin-off development.	0.769
<i>Subjective norms</i> (AVE=.98; α=.99; rhoA=.99)	
My choice to leave the country will involve most of the people who are important to me regard me as clever.	0.995
My choice to leave the country will involve most of the people who are important to me to regard it as useful.	0.994
My choice to leave the country will involve most of the people who are important to me to regard it as valuable.	0.992
<i>Higher education quality</i> (AVE=.82; α=.92; rhoA=.92)	
University constitutional recognition.	0.840
University educational quality.	0.898
Faculty educational quality.	0.943
Undergrad educational quality.	0.932
<i>Professors' availability*</i> (AVE=.79; α=.13; rhoA=.93)	
Professors at this faculty get annoyed when students try to talk to him/her outside of class or office hours.	0.905
I find it difficult to approach my professors outside of class.	0.896
Professors at this faculty seem distant when interacting with students outside of class.	0.860
Professors at this faculty discourage student contact outside of class.	0.899
<i>Intention to leave the country</i> (AVE=.71; α=.80; rhoA=.81)	
I will move abroad in the near future.	0.888
I often think about leaving the county.	0.885
I would like to remain in the county.	0.761

Table 2. Measurement model valuation

Note: All loadings are significant at confidence level $p < 0.05$; * Reverse code variable.

Table 3. Heterotrait-monotrait ratio

	ILC	SE	HEQ	PA	SN
ILC
SE	0.101
HEQ	0.301	0.584	.	.	.
PA	0.183	0.047	0.168	.	.
SN	0.611	0.028	0.143	0.132	.

Note: ILC – intention to leave the country, SE- students’ expectations, HEQ – higher education quality, PA- professors’ availability, SN – subjective norms

Table 4. Structural model valuation

Path	β (t-statistics)	p-values	Result
H1a: SE → HEQ	0.498 (20.76)	0.000***	Supported
H1b: SE → PA	-0.002 (0.05)	0.957 ^{ns}	Not Supported
H1c: SE → ILC	0.083 (2.95)	0.003**	Supported
H2a: SN → HEQ	-0.124 (5.24)	0.000***	Supported
H2b: SN → PA	0.128 (4.60)	0.000**	Supported
H2c: SN → ILC	0.512 (22.43)	0.000***	Supported
H3: HEQ → ILC	-0.216 (7.11)	0.000**	Supported
H4: PA → ILC	0.064 (2.46)	0.014*	Supported

Note: SE- students’ expectations, IQ – higher education quality, PU- professors’ availability, SN – subjective norms, ITC – intention to leave the country; *** p< 0.001, ** p<0.01, * p<0.05, ns – not significant

Table 5. Indirect effects

Indirect effect	β (t-statistics)	p-values
Students' expectations → Higher education quality → Intention to leave the country	-0.107 (6.55)	0.000***
Students' expectations → Professors' availability → Intention to leave the country	0.008 (2.145)	0.034*
Subjective norms → Higher education quality → Intention to leave the country	0.027 (4.326)	0.000***
Subjective norms → Professors' availability → Intention to leave the country	0.000 (0.05)	0.961 ^{ns}

Note: *** p< 0.001, * p<0.05, ns – not significant